

turboSPH Performance Evaluation

bwRSE4HPC Project Proposal

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Project Partners:	Rainer Koch ² , Niklas Bürkle
Scientific field:	Engineering
Subfield:	Combustion
Start:	24.02.2026
Duration:	5 Weeks
Type of Work:	Performance Evaluation
License:	Proprietary
Link:	Not available
Programming Language:	C++
Technologies:	MPI
Target Cluster:	HoreKa

1. Project Summary

Reducing emissions is key to achieving sustainable aviation. One significant aspect, especially with regard to pollutants, is the fuel injection with the key phenomenon of atomization. The research group of Rainer Koch has developed the code `turboSPH` to simulate this and other related aspects. Its methodology is described in the dissertation by C. Höfler [1] and S. Braun [2]. While the code was initially very efficient, the current performance is no longer satisfactory. To better understand the issue, this project will present a thorough performance evaluation of turboSPH, pinpointing the underlying performance issue. Suggestions on how to resolve these issues will be presented and may guide any follow-up projects to optimize turboSPH.

2. Problem Statement

The code turboSPH has been continuously developed over the last 15 years. New models were added to simulate complex physical phenomena more accurately. However, over time, the performance has degraded and is no longer satisfactory. In its current state, simulations with turboSPH can be summarized as follows:

- Up to 450 million particles.
- Between 500 thousand and one million time steps.
- Up to two thousand CPU cores on HoreKa.
- About 0.2s per time step, for a total simulation time of over 50h.

The underlying issues for the insufficient performance are unclear. Several performance issues have been observed. For one, the scaling efficiency is not ideal; see Figure 1. The

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Figure 1: Scaling Efficiency

Figure 2: FLOP/s Performance on Horeka

performance already drops within a single node, and it drops again for a very large number of processes. Additionally, the computational load seems to be imbalanced. In Figure 2 it can be seen that some processes only achieve $\frac{2}{3}$ FLOP/s of the best performing process. However, these findings are insufficient to decide which optimizations should be applied to turboSPH.

3. Suggested Solution

The bwRSE4HPC team proposes to conduct a thorough performance evaluation on the relevant target cluster. They will define interesting performance metrics, such as FLOP/s, memory bandwidth, cache misses, and inter-process communication latency and bandwidth, which will be used to measure the application. Additionally, the call tree and traces of the program will be analyzed. This enables connecting certain parts of the code to specific performance issues. The experimentation will include a reproducibility statement to simplify repeating the evaluation in the future.

4. Milestones

The work is structured along the following milestones:

- Week 1** Independently run small and large test cases.
- Week 3** Define metrics and suitable tooling.
- Week 5** Gather performance characteristics.

5. Deliverables

The deliverable outcome of this project will be a performance evaluation report. This report will be combined with the project's final report. The report will contain:

- Description of the performance characteristics.
- Hardware and software setup for data gathering.
- Scripts used for measurements or data analysis.
- Suggestions on how to improve performance issues.

6. Expected Contributions

To ensure a successful collaboration, the partners agree to contribute the following:

- Access to the source code.
- Access to computing resources on the target cluster.
- Point of contact within the group of Rainer Koch for (semi-)regular exchange.
- Relevant test cases in different sizes.

- Acknowledgement of the RSEs in publications which contain significant contributions from the RSEs.

Bibliography

- [1] C. Höfler, “Entwicklung eines Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) Codes zur numerischen Vorhersage des Primärzerfalls an Brennstoffeinspritzdüsen [Überarbeitete Version],” Doctoral dissertation, Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT), 2013. doi: [10.5445/IR/1000048880](https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:hbz:5:1-63888-p0011-9) .
- [2] S. Braun, “Zur Simulation der Zerstäubung flüssigen Kraftstoffs mit der Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics Methode,” Doctoral dissertation, Logos Verlag Berlin, 2018.